

Twin prime conjecture

additional proof

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In previous proof,

for the parameter of Twin Field k , (k is used to express $(6k \pm 1)$)

the k that is eliminated from twin primes is when

$$k_y = (6n - 1)m \pm n$$

$$k_o = (6n + 1)m \pm n$$

k_y means \times younger brother set

k_o means \times older brother set

Anyway, among the components of this equation, $(6n - 1)$, n are such that

$$n \leq \frac{(6n - 1)}{5}$$

for all n .

Let's prove it by induction.

i) $n = 1$

$$1 \leq \frac{(6 - 1)}{5} = 1$$

inequality holds

Now we assume that

$$n \leq \frac{(6n - 1)}{5}$$

holds for any natural number n .

Now we substitute $n = n + 1$

$$n + 1 \leq \frac{\{6(n + 1) - 1\}}{5}$$

$$n + 1 \leq \frac{6n + 5}{5}$$

$$n + 1 \leq \frac{6n}{5} + 1$$

$$n \leq \frac{6n}{5}$$

inequality holds!

the components $(6n + 1), n$ also satisfies the relationship

$$n \leq \frac{(6n + 1)}{5}$$

What this mean is

when we survey elimination by each $(6n \pm 1)$,

elimination occurs at both extremes of the k number array.

For example, elimination by 5 is

$$k = 5m \pm 1$$

array

$$k = 4,6,9,11,14,16,19,21 \dots$$

What they have in common is that only the numbers at the ends of the array are dropped in the order of 5.

How many of the k 's out of 100 will survive?

$$N = 100$$

predicted by my previous way:

$$100 \times \frac{3}{5} = 60$$

actual number of survivors: 61.

Why? Because in the sequence $k = 5m \pm 1$,

1 is not included in the elimination.

So my predict: $60 < 61$ (actual survivors)

60 is minimum lower bound of my way, and it is also smaller than actual survivors.

How about $N=101$?

predict: $101 \times \frac{3}{5} = 60.6$ (a minimum lower bound)

actual: 61

So my predict : $60.6 < 61$ (actual survivors)

$N=102$? 103 ?

Since elimination occur at both extremes,

$N=102 \rightarrow 62$ actual survivors

predict $102 \times \frac{3}{5} = 61.2 < 62$

$N=103 \rightarrow 63$ actual survivors

predict $103 \times \frac{3}{5} = 61.8 < 63$

$N=104 \rightarrow 63$ actual survivors

predict $104 \times \frac{3}{5} = 62.4 < 63$

In general,

$$N = 5k + c, (0 \leq c \leq 4)$$

$$\text{actual survivor}(N=5k) : 5k \times \frac{3}{5} + 1 = 3k + 1$$

$$\text{predicted survivor}(N=5k) : 5k \times \frac{3}{5} = 3k$$

predict $3k < 3k+1$ actual

$$N = 5k + 1$$

actual survivor ($N=5k+1$): $3k + 1$ (same as $N=5k$)

$$\text{predicted survivor}(N=5k+1) : (5k + 1) \times \frac{3}{5} = 3k + 0.6$$

predicted: $3k+0.6 < 3k+1$ actual

$$N = 5k + 2$$

actual survivor: $3k + 2$

$$\text{predicted: } (5k + 2) \times \frac{3}{5} = 3k + 1.2$$

predicted $3k+1.2 < 3k+2$ actual

$$N = 5k + 3$$

actual survivor ($N=5k+3$): $3k+3$

predicted survivor ($N=5k+3$): $(5k + 3) \times \frac{3}{5} = 3k + 1.8$

predicted $3k+1.8 < 3k+3$ actual

$$N = 5k + 4$$

actual survivor ($N=5k+4$): $3k+3$

predicted survivor ($N=5k+4$): $(5k + 4) \times \frac{3}{5} = 3k + 2.4$

predicted $3k+2.4 < 3k+3$ actual

Therefore, for all k , predicted survivor (=minimum lower bound) is always smaller than actual survivor ! (about 5)

In general again,

$$k = (6n - 1)m \pm n$$

survey by period $(6n - 1)$

survivors until $N = (6n - 1)z$ is

$$(6n - 1)z \times \frac{(6n - 3)}{(6n - 1)} + 1 = (6n - 3)z + 1$$

predicted value is

$$(6n - 1)z \times \frac{(6n - 3)}{(6n - 1)} = (6n - 3)z$$

Actual survivors until $N = (6n - 1)z + c$ ($1 \leq c \leq \frac{6n}{2}$) is
always hold following inequality:

$$(6n - 3)z + c \leq \text{actual survivor}$$

predicted value:

$$\{(6n - 1)z + c\} \times \frac{(6n - 3)}{(6n - 1)} = (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 3)c}{(6n - 1)}$$

$$\left\{ (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 3)c}{(6n - 1)} \right\} \text{ vs } \{(6n - 3)z + c\}$$

(predicted) vs (actual survivor)

What is the bigger one?

$$\begin{aligned} & (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 3)c}{(6n - 1)} \\ &= (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 1 - 2)c}{(6n - 1)} \\ &= (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 1)c - 2c}{(6n - 1)} \\ &= (6n - 3)z + c - \frac{2c}{(6n - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$(6n - 3)z + c - \frac{2c}{(6n - 1)} < (6n - 3)z + c$$

inequality always holds !

Therefore we can sure that

minimum lower bound < actual survivor

$$\text{for } N = (6n - 1)z + c \quad (0 \leq c \leq \frac{6n}{2})$$

Now, let's prove about

$$N = (6n - 1)z + c \quad \left(\frac{6n}{2} < c < 6n - 1 \right)$$

$$(6n - 3)z + 1 + c - 2 < (\text{actual survivors})$$

predicted until $N = (6n - 1)z + c$ is

$$\{(6n - 1)z + c\} \times \frac{(6n - 3)}{(6n - 1)} = (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 3)c}{(6n - 1)}$$

$$\{(6n - 3)z + c - 1\} \text{ vs } \left\{ (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 3)c}{(6n - 1)} \right\}$$

actual vs predicted

Which is the bigger one?

$$\begin{aligned} (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 3)c}{(6n - 1)} &= (6n - 3)z + \frac{(6n - 1 - 2)c}{(6n - 1)} \\ &= (6n - 3)z + c - \frac{2c}{(6n - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

Since $(3n < c < 6n - 1)$,

$$6n < 2c < 12n - 2$$

$$1 < \frac{2c}{(6n - 1)} < 2$$

Therefore,

$$(6n - 3)z + c - \frac{2c}{(6n - 1)} < (6n - 3)z + c - 1$$

(predicted) < (actual)

least lower bound < actual

Therefore, the inequality always holds!

About the proof $(6k+1)$ is similar to this $(6k-1)$ proof.

Therefore, the minimum remaining ratio until $k = N$:

$$N \times \frac{3}{5} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{9}{11} \times \dots$$

each remaining are always bigger than the number of actual remaining of k !

Thank you for reading.